

rice yields in both seasons: + 1.0 t/ha in the dry season, + 0.5 t/ha in the wet season (see figure). Rice yields increased with increased N. Highest yield in the

dry season was with 200 kg N/ha; and with 100 kg N/ha in the wet season. Green gram yields did not vary

significantly with residual green manure or applied N at rates above 100 kg N/ha. □

Residual effect of fertilizer applied to rice in rice - fallow - cotton

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In Cauvery delta of south India, rice - rice - cotton and rice - cotton are common crop rotations. We evaluated the effect of fertilizer applied to the second season rice crop on rice - fallow - cotton during 1987 and 1988.

Experiment field soil was Entic Chromustert with pH 7.4, CEC 30.8 meq/100 g, 0.75% organic C, 295-15-325 kg available NPK/ha and E.C. 0.2 dS/m.

The experiment was laid out in a split-plot design. Main plot treatments were rice with no fertilizer and 100 kg N, 22 kg P, and 42 kg K/ha individually and in combination. The subplots were

Residual effect of fertilizer applied to rice on cotton yields in a rice - fallow - cotton rotation. Aduthurai, India, 1987-88.

Fertilizer to rice (kg NPK/ha)	Yield (t/ha)							
	Fertilizers applied to cotton							
	First year			Mean	Second year			Mean
	0-0-0	60-13-25	30-6.5-12.5		0-0-0	60-13-25	30-6.5-12.5	
0-0-0	1.0	1.4	1.4	1.3	1.4	1.7	1.5	1.5
100-0-0	1.3	1.5	1.4	1.4	1.6	1.9	1.9	1.8
100-22-0	1.5	1.6	1.5	1.5	1.5	1.9	1.8	1.7
100-0-42	1.5	1.6	1.6	1.6	1.9	1.9	2.0	2.0
100-22-42	1.6	1.7	1.7	1.6	1.5	2.1	1.7	1.8
Mean	1.4	1.6	1.5		1.6	1.9	1.8	
LSD between 2 fertilizer treatments of rice at different levels of fertilizer to cotton				0.7				1.7
LSD between 2 fertilizer treatments of cotton at different levels of fertilizer to rice				1.0				2.4

rice - fallow - cotton (MCU7) with no fertilizer, 60-13-25 kg NPK/ha and 30-6.5-12.5 kg NPK/ha.

Half the fertilizer recommended for cotton was adequate, since the residual

effect of 100-0-42 kg NPK/ha applied to the preceding rice crop was pronounced (see table). The residual effect of P on cotton was negligible. □

Effect of source and level of nitrogen on yield of rice and succeeding lentil crop

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We studied the residual effect of urea and modified urea on yields of rice and a succeeding lentil crop grown without fertilizer 1986-87 and 1987-88.

The soil was sandy to clay loam with pH 8.1; 0.38% organic C, 10 kg available P/ha, 233 kg available K/ha. Wet season rice was followed by dry season lentil in a randomized block design with four replications.

N source had a significant residual effect on the succeeding lentil yield (see table). Urea supergranule (USG) deep placement in rice had the highest

Effect of source and level of N on grain yield of rice and the residual effect on lentil yield. Crop Research Station, Ghagharaghat, India, 1986-87 and 1987-88.

Treatment	Rice yield (t/ha)		Lentil yield (t/ha)	
	1986	1987	1986	1987
<i>Nitrogen sources</i>				
Prilled urea (1/2 basal + 1/2 topdressed after first flood receded)	2.0	1.7	1.2	1.1
Prilled urea (1/2 basal + 1/2 foliar spray after first flood receded)	2.0	1.6	1.2	1.0
Lac-coated urea (basal)	2.7	2.4	1.3	1.2
Neem-coated urea (basal)	2.8	2.6	1.4	1.3
Urea supergranules (placed 8-10 cm deep after first flood receded)	2.9	2.8	1.7	1.6
LSD (0.05)	0.2	0.2	0.2	0.2
<i>Nitrogen level (kg/ha)</i>				
0	1.1	1.1	0.9	0.8
30	2.7	2.5	1.3	1.2
60	2.9	2.7	1.5	1.4
LSD (0.05)	0.2	0.2	0.1	0.1

residual effect on lentil yield; neem-coated urea (basal) and USG did not differ statistically. Prilled urea in 2 splits had very low residual effect.

The increase in lentil yield after

modified urea applied to rice is explained by the significantly lower loss of N through leaching, denitrification, and ammoniacal volatilization. □